

Corrigendum:
Filled pauses and false starts do not reliably preface longer or more complex utterances across typologically diverse languages.
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Corrigendum

1) At the end of Section 2.1, the following paragraph should be added:

The datasets used in this study are: [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61].

2) The reference section was missing 51 entries. The updated and complete reference section is presented on the following pages.

7. References

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